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THE GREEN WIRELESS NETWORKS:

BUILDING ENERGY- & EMF-AWARE

NETWORKS

WWRF 49, Prof. dr. ir. Margot Deruyck, 28/03/2023

sustainability

Meaning of sustainability in English

sustainability

noun [U]

UK /səˈsteɪ.nəˈbɪl.ə.ti/ US /səˈsteɪ.nəˈbɪl.ə.tj/

the quality of being able to continue over a period of time:

- *the long-term sustainability of the community*

C2 ENVIRONMENT

the quality of causing little or no damage to the environment and therefore able to continue for a long time:

- *the company's commitment to environmental sustainability*

ICT SECTOR: HUGE EMISSIONS

Source: C. Freitag et al., *The climate impact of ICT: A review of estimates, trends and regulations*, arXiv: 2102.02622v1

Carbon footprint of ICT is systematically underestimated
& could actually be as high as **2.1 to 3.9%**

THE FUTURE?

Business as usual:

- Most realistic: exponential growth
- Up to 2.5 GtCO₂e in 2030
Up to 5.2 GtCO₂e in 2040
- Explosion of data traffic driven by trends like AI, Blockchain and IoT
- Slowing down of efficiency improvement

Source: C. Freitag et al., *The climate impact of ICT: A review of estimates, trends and regulations*, arXiv: 2102.02622v1

WHAT ABOUT THE NETWORK?

Source: C. Freitag et al., *The climate impact of ICT: A review of estimates, trends and regulations*, arXiv: 2102.02622v1

THE WIRELESS NETWORK

Main contributor: the base station

Table 1 | Comparison between a 4G and a 5G macro base station

Transmission power /bandwidth	MIMO	Base band (W)	RRU (W)	Total power (W) 4x	Throughput (Mbps) 16x
4G LTE (40 W @ 20 MHz)	8T8R	150	950	1,100	120
5G NR (240 W @ 100 MHz)	64T64R	220	4,077	4,297	1,963

The measurements were carried out by China Mobile in 2019, using base stations manufactured by world leading vendors. LTE, long term evolution; NR, new radio

Source: I. et al, *Energy-efficient 5G for a greener future*, Nature Electronics, Vol. 3, No. 4, pp. 182-184, 2020.

But hasn't the BS become more energy-efficient?

YES: 16x larger throughput for 4x larger power consumption

BUT NO: larger power consumption → denser network → forecast: total energy consumption of 5G will increase by 150-170% by 2026!!!

HOW CAN WE IMPROVE?

Careful selection of the BS locations (& settings)
based on actual user requirement

GRAND: GREEN RADIO ACCESS NETWORK DESIGN

Wireless outdoor network planner

- 3D environment
- Number of simultaneous active users in the target area
- Location distribution
- Bit rate distribution
- Time stamp

→ Combined in a traffic file used as input for the tool

GRAND - ALGORITHM

– Multi-objective function

$$O = \frac{-w_0 \cdot U_{sol}}{U_{max}} + \frac{w_1 \cdot PL_{sol}}{PL_{max}} + \frac{w_2 \cdot PC_{sol}}{PC_{max}}$$

- How well does solution perform compare to worst case scenario?
- Worst case: all BS on, max power

EXAMPLE: 4G IN BRUSSELS

Original network

- 289 base stations
- (user) coverage $\geq 95\%$
- 7.1 kWh power consumption

Optimized network

- 188 base stations
 - (user) coverage $\geq 95\%$
 - 4.7 kWh power consumption
- 33.4% better**

CAN WE DO MORE?

- Renewable energy

RENEWABLE ENERGY

- Applied on a small-scale environment for 4G
- **Up to 89% till 96.6% of the total power consumption** can be provided through renewables
- Optimistic: no losses for transportation/battery (dis)charging, placement of the renewable power plants, etc.

ENVIRONMENT-
FRIENDLY

EXPOSURE AWARENESS

– Multi-objective function

$$O = \frac{-w_0 \cdot U_{sol}}{U_{max}} + \frac{w_1 \cdot PL_{sol}}{PL_{max}} + \frac{w_2 \cdot DL_{sol}}{DL_{max}} + \frac{w_3 \cdot UL_{sol}}{UL_{max}}$$

- How well does solution perform compare to worst case scenario?
- Worst case: all BS on, max power

GRAND – EXPOSURE EVALUATION

User

DL exposure: whole body

UL exposure: localized 10g

$$SAR_{DL_{wb}} = SAR_{DL_{wb}}^{REF} \cdot \sum_{j=0}^n S_{BSj}$$

$$SAR_{UL_{10g}} = SAR_{UL_{10g}}^{REF} \cdot P_n \cdot DC_{TDD}^{UL}$$

$$ER_{DL} = \frac{1}{T_{REF}} \cdot \frac{SAR_{DL_{wb}}}{SAR_{lim_{wb}}} \cdot T_{DL}$$

$$ER_{UL} = \frac{1}{T_{REF}} \cdot \frac{SAR_{UL_{10g}}}{SAR_{lim_{10g}}} \cdot T_{UL}$$

$$ER = ER_{DL} + ER_{UL}$$

n Users → *n* ER values

Network exposure E_{tot}

p_{50} or p_{95} over all individual ER values

Dimensionless
Exposure Ratio

STUDY CONCEPT OVERVIEW

USE CASES

Use Case 1: 4G → 10Mbps
5G → 100Mbps
UL and DL Optimization.

Use Case 2: 4G → 10Mbps
5G → 100Mbps
Only DL Optimization.

Use Case 3: 4G → 5% users 100Mbps
5G → 5% users 1Gbps
UL and DL Optimization

SCENARIOS

100% Outdoor: All the users are placed in outdoor locations.

Indoor: Users are located in random locations but at least 25% should be located in indoor locations.

Indoor 15m: Users are randomly located and at least 25% must be indoor. Indoor users must be located only in building with a side less than 15m.

ENVIRONMENTS

Urban → Zurich
Suburban → Giubiasco
Rural → Hüttwilen

OPERATORS

Swisscom
Sunrise
Salt
Unified Network

- 4G: 800 MHz & 2100 MHz
- 5G: 800 MHz, 2100 MHz & 3500 MHz (MaMIMO)

USE CASE ZURICH

URBAN: Zurich

RESULTS

Number of base stations

Exposure ratio

- 5G about 2x more BS than 4G but larger throughput!
- 5G exposure is about 1.3x larger but larger throughput!

A close-up photograph of a hand holding two wooden blocks. The top block has the number '5' and the bottom block has the number '6'. To the right of these two blocks is another wooden block with the letter 'G'. The blocks are resting on a wooden surface. The background is a soft, out-of-focus light blue.

5

6

G

A hand is holding a black rectangular sign with the text "5G" written in large, white, bold, sans-serif font. The background is dark with a glowing, out-of-focus network diagram consisting of white nodes and connecting lines, suggesting a digital or communication theme.

5G

SUSTAINABLE

